

Conference Abstract

Genetic Enhancement of Weatherfish Populations via Targeted Breeding Programs

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Abstract

Many populations of the weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis* L.) in north-western Europe have experienced significant declines since the end of the Second World War. These declines have been largely attributed to changes in land use practices, such as agricultural intensification and urban development, as well as a deterioration in water quality across their natural habitats. Several of the remaining weatherfish populations are currently characterized by poor conservation status. Decades of habitat fragmentation have resulted in reduced genetic diversity, increased levels of inbreeding, and the presence of phantom populations—small, isolated groups that are demographically unstable and genetically unsustainable in the long term. Although traditional approaches to aquatic restoration—such as habitat enhancement, water quality improvement, and the removal of migration barriers—remain essential and should be prioritized, they are often insufficient to recover genetically depleted populations. To support the recovery of these populations, a targeted breeding program was developed, funded by LIFE B4B, for the weatherfish. This involved introducing genetic material from populations with high genetic diversity into extant, inbred populations. Over recent years, the protocol for artificial reproduction has been gradually optimised, resulting in a stable and scalable production of large numbers of juvenile weatherfish. In parallel, a release program for this endangered species was implemented in Flanders. Thousands of farmed young-of-the-year individuals were introduced at eight sites within the species' historical range. Additionally, as part of a complementary reintroduction strategy, tens of thousands of

juvenile fish (2–4 weeks old, 10–20 mm in length) were released into carefully selected river sectors. Recent monitoring at one of the release sites revealed encouraging results, with high survival rates and numerous juveniles originating from natural recruitment. While it is still too early to declare the project a definitive success, the re-establishment of natural reproduction represents a critical first milestone. Ongoing genetic analyses will be necessary to assess the extent of admixture between the introduced genetic lines and the resident populations (Suppl. material 1).

Presenting author

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Genetic Enhancement of Weatherfish Populations via Targeted Breeding Programs [doi](#)

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